

OCEAN ICE News – September 2025

OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to September's edition of OCEAN ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, OCEAN ICE at BACO2025, highlighting June and August's Climate Coffee. We have some upcoming Climate Coffee's that you can register for in September, October and November. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in October!

Researcher in the Spotlight: Marte Hofsteenge

Check out our latest 'Researcher in the Spotlight' feature on Marte Hofsteenge, a postdoctoral researcher at Utrecht University in the Netherlands.

Read the feature on Marte [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN ICE Activities

OCEAN ICE at BACO 2025

Pierre Dutrieux from British Antarctic Survey and co-lead of WP1 presented OCEAN ICE work at [BACO 2025](#) in South Korea back in July and presented on Wednesday, 23 July 2025, 09:00 - 10:30. Pierre was an invited speaker and his talk was titled 'The West Antarctic Ice Sheet Response to Tropical Forcing: a 30-year long observational perspective'.

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – June

Catch up on June's Climate Coffee with Pietro Viglino: Jupyter Notebooks: How to implement them, Drawing on OCEAN ICE experience [here](#).

What this webinar is about: The Horizon Europe-funded project OCEAN ICE adheres to open science practices and supports the publication of complementary materials that facilitate the reuse of the project's data. One key tool is the OCEAN ICE literacy portal, which provides instructions and examples about creating new research products using Jupyter Notebooks, which are openly available for testing and further use. In this talk, after a short introduction about how to interact with OCEAN ICE's data service (ERDDAP) using Python, the participants will be guided through the exploration of these data and their visualization in a Jupyter environment. In this way, the participants will obtain the tools to play with code using the same data typology that is used in the Notebooks available in open access for the OCEAN ICE project.

12 June 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST

Online

Pietro Viglino (ETT)

Jupyter Notebooks: How to implement them, drawing on the experience in the OCEAN ICE project

Danish Meteorological Institute

OCEAN:ICE

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OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – August

Climate Coffee with Amina Ben Salah on A Copula-Based Approach to Explore Climate-Driven Ocean Variability In the Gibraltar Strait.

What this webinar is about This study investigates the impact of climate change on small pelagic fish stocks by modelling the complex relationships between sea surface temperature (SST) and chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) concentration. These two variables serve as key indicators of oceanic conditions that influence the abundance of marine organisms. A copula-based modelling approach is employed to assess these dependencies using satellite-derived data from MODISA and climate hindcast models. The analysis focuses on the Strait of Gibraltar, a biologically productive and climate-sensitive region. It considers seasonal variations by analyzing the March–April–May (MAM) and September–October–November (SON) periods. The marginal distributions and copulas are first fitted to historical observations, then applied to model data. A multivariate bias correction method is used to enhance the model simulations. This framework provides a foundation for understanding long-term changes in ocean dynamics and their potential effects on fisheries.

The study has been published recently: <https://link.springer.com/article/10...>

This presentation is available on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/16964854>

Our speaker Amina Ben Salah is a Moroccan PhD candidate in her third year under the MICODIR project. Her research focuses on modelling small pelagic fish stocks using advanced statistical methods, particularly the application of copula-based approaches to study climate–marine ecosystem interactions

28 August 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Amina Ben Salah (UAE)

**A Copula-Based Approach to Explore
Climate-Driven Ocean Variability in the
Strait of Gibraltar**

Danish Meteorological Institute

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the European Union

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have an upcoming Climate Coffee in August, September, October and November, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN ICE](#).

Climate Coffee with Audrey Minière on Estimating ocean warming: Challenges & recommendations for robust assessment

25 September 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

25 September 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST
Online

Audrey Minière (ENS)

Estimating ocean warming: challenges
and recommendations for robust
assessment

Danish Meteorological Institute

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the European Union

Climate Coffee with Blanca Fernández Álvarez on How Detection Frameworks Shape Our View of 2024's Mediterranean MHW

30 October 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

30 October 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET
Online

Blanca Fernández-Álvarez (IMEDEA-
CSIC)

How Detection Frameworks Shape Our
View of 2024's Mediterranean Marine
Heatwaves

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Climate Coffee with Natacha Legrix De La Salle on Surface and Subsurface Compound MHW and Biogeochemical Extremes Under Climate Change.
27 November 2025, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

27 November 2025 | 10:00 - 10:45 CET
Online
Natacha Legrix De La Salle (Univ. Liverpool)
Surface and Subsurface Compound
Marine Heatwave and Biogeochemical
Extremes Under Climate Change

Danish Meteorological Institute

Funded by
the European Union

Save the Date: 15-17 September 2025 – OCEAN ICE Annual Project Meeting, Copenhagen

Save the dates for the OCEAN ICE Annual Project Meeting, 15-17 September 2025, which will be kindly hosted by the Danish Meteorological Institute in Copenhagen, Denmark and online.

OCEAN ICE WP5 Webinar: Ice Sheet Impacts on Global Ocean Circulation

WP5 investigates how ice sheet meltwater discharge affects deep water formation, pole-to-pole connections, and large-scale ocean circulation, including the AMOC and ACC. This session combines new ocean observations, innovative analyses, and modelling approaches to better understand how freshwater influences the global climate system.

The programme begins with new observational results: the first sustained time series from the South Sandwich Trench and updated evidence of changes in South Atlantic water mass properties. We then move to data integration, with an analysis of “water mass archaeology” to trace the movement of water masses from the deep ocean to the surface. The final section focuses on modelling studies, highlighting the Southern Ocean’s response to Antarctic meltwater and the wider global impacts of freshwater forcing.

Date and time: October 7, 14:00-15:30 CEST

Programme:

Introduction

Petra Langebroek & Elaine McDonagh (NORCE)

New Observations

The first time series of deep observations from the South Sandwich Trench – Rachael Sanders (BAS)

New observations on water mass properties changes in the South Atlantic – Zhetao Tan (IPSL)

Data Analysis

Water Mass Archaeology: Tracing water masses to the surface – Xabier Davila (NORCE)

Modelling Results

The response of the Southern Ocean to recent and projected Antarctic meltwater changes – Birte Gürk (LOCEAN)

Global impacts of freshwater forcing – David Chandler (NORCE)

Q&A & Discussion

Register here: https://us02web.zoom.us/webinar/register/WN_GXkpN0hZR3qJ2WZC65shhg

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OCEAN ICE webinar series is facilitated by the [European Polar Board](#).

OCEAN ICE WP5 WEBINAR

ICE SHEET IMPACTS ON GLOBAL OCEAN CIRCULATION

This webinar is part of the series introducing
the EU-funded OCEAN ICE project.

Register here:

© Dr. Renuka Badhe

7 October 2025
14:00 CEST

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

Happening Soon

OCEAN ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 9th – 10th September 2025, 07:00–09:30 UTC, 15:00–17:30 UTC, [Antarctica InSync International Science Webinar](#)
- 25th-26th September, [The All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance \(AAORIA\)](#), Brussels, Belgium
- 29th – 31st October, [Nordic Branch of IGS Meeting](#), Copenhagen Denmark
- 18th November 2025, Policy Briefing, Brussels, Belgium
- 9th – 12th Feb 2026, [Open Science Conference](#), New Zealand
- 22nd – 27th February 2025, [Ocean Sciences Meeting](#), Glasgow, Scotland
- 9th – 13th March 2026, [CMIP 2026 Meeting](#), Kyoto, Japan

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

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<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

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<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

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[OCEAN ICE \(@oceaniceeu.bsky.social\) — Bluesky](#)

Who is OCEAN ICE?

OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

 OCEAN:ICE

UK Partners are funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding Guarantee.

OCEAN ICE is funded by the European Union, Horizon Europe Funding Programme for research and innovation under grant agreement Nr. 101060452.